

CFD BASED SIMULATIONS FOR THERMAL MANAGEMENT OF LITHIUM-ION CELL USING PHASE CHANGE MATERIAL

Muhammad Zahid^{*1}, Annie Ilyas²^{*1,2}Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Southern Punjab, Multan 66000, Pakistan^{*1}muhammadzahid82@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18655268>**Keywords**

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Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Zahid

Abstract

In the current manuscript, the impact of cell enclosure design on melting of phase change material has been investigated for the purpose of thermal management of lithium-ion cell. For this, we considered two designs of cell enclosure namely, Simple Enclosure and Finned Enclosure. The Simple Enclosure surrounds the phase change material RT-27 which is mounted around the cell. The Finned Enclosure differs Simple Enclosure such a way that it has five circular fins on the inner side distributed uniformly along the length. These fins are embedded into the phase change material which touch the cell. The cell top is the boundary with constant and uniform heat flux of 2500 W/m^2 . The transient simulations are run for both designs until complete melt of the phase change material. The comparison of the results reveals the significance of fins for uniformly distributing the temperature into the phase change material to avoid the cell deformation or damage. The simulations are run on ANSYS Workbench with enabling the energy and melting/solidification models in the FLUENT. A mesh independence test has also been conducted for the validity of the model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional fossil-fuel engines are a major source of air pollution because of releasing harmful gases such as carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, and particulate matter into the atmosphere. These emissions contribute to smog, respiratory problems, and global climate change. With the increase in population, the increase in transportation requirements are making the environmental situations even more serious. For this reason, lithium-ion batteries are attractive cleaner alternative to the conventional fossil-fuel engines. In electric vehicles, lithium-ion batteries function as high-energy on-board storage units that supply power for propulsion, auxiliary functions, and regenerative braking. With the increasing demand for higher energy density and faster charging, managing the thermal behavior of lithium-ion batteries has become

a critical requirement for the continued advancement of sustainable electric mobility.

To address these thermal challenges, researchers and engineers are increasingly exploring advanced battery thermal management systems (BTMS), including those based on phase change materials (PCMs). An effective thermal management or thermal regulation system is necessary for maintaining cell temperature within an optimal range, ensuring stable performance, and preventing degradation or safety hazards. PCMs offer a passive and energy-efficient solution by absorbing excess heat during their melting process while maintaining a nearly constant temperature. When incorporated around battery cells, they help control temperature rise, minimize thermal gradients, and enhance overall system reliability. This makes PCM-based thermal

management a promising approach for modern electric vehicle battery packs.

Lithium-ion batteries have been proven to be amongst best and dominant energy storage systems due to their high energy density, increased lifespan, and having ability of rapid power delivery when compared with the other battery technologies. However, the performance of the is directly related to the temperature [1-2] which must be controlled to keep it in a limit for the enhanced performance and safety. The temperature of the batteries increases due to significant thermal energy production during charge and discharge processes under operational conditions because of resistive heating and exothermic electrochemical reactions. In case of failure in thermal regulation of the batteries, there will be consequences to face, like thermal runaway and damage in batteries which poses a direct risk to both the safety and performance reliability of the batteries.

It means that the temperature has a critical role in efficient and longevity of lithium-ion batteries because high temperature accelerates cell degradation and reduces energy storage capacity. Therefore, making batteries cost effective and using in vehicles with long-life span, it is necessary to introduce and implement optimal and effective thermal management. The thermal management may either be active or passive. The active battery thermal management systems are either air-based cooling systems [3-4] or liquid-based cooling systems [5-6]. The passive type of battery thermal management systems (BTMS) are based on natural principles which are PCMs and heat pipes. The paraffin was the PCM first used by Hallaj and Selman [7] for BTMS. They performed simulations for the temperature distribution profiles in a 100 Ah battery comprising 18650 cells and revealed that the PCM lowered the battery temperature significantly when compared with the battery without PCM. Kizilel et al. [8] also used PCM for the passive thermal management of lithium-ion batteries. Their analysis revealed that incorporating PCM significantly enhances the safety of batteries because the risk of their thermal runaway minimizes and their overall thermal efficiency improves. Further, their results showed that PCM-based cooling provides better thermal control than conventional forced-air methods. Limin Song [9]

developed and simulated a passive BTMS using PCM, offering a detailed assessment of the thermal regulation of a battery and the melting characteristics of the PCM.

The lower thermal conductivity of PCMs make them less responsive to the highly heat generating sources to use them effectively and efficiently [10]. To overcome this deficiency, recent studies proposed some techniques like use of metallic nanoparticles along with the PCMs [11-13], inserting fins in the PCMs [14] and metallic foams or metal matrix [15-17], etc. For making the thermal management system even more relying on PCMs, different layers of difference PCMs are also used [18-20]. The finned containers are also used to improve the thermal storage performance. Taghilou and Talati [21,22] used rectangular finned container for their numerical study on the melting and freezing of PCM.

In the current study, we use RT-27 PCM for the purpose of thermal management of a lithium-ion 18650 cell during operational conditions, while a simple aluminum enclosure and a finned aluminum enclosure are used to hold the PCM around the cell.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The cell under consideration is a lithium-ion 18650 cell. A 3 mm thick layer of RT-27 PCM is mounted circumferentially around the cell for the thermal management. To hold the cell and the PCM, an enclosure is required which may be a simple hollow metallic cylinder, or a geometrically manipulated metallic cylinder to distribute the heat uniformly into the PCM. For this, we consider two designs of enclosure namely, the Simple Enclosure and the Finned Enclosure. These enclosures are made-up of aluminum sheet of thickness 1 mm. The fin thickness is also 1 mm. The Simple Enclosure holds simply the PCM and the cell. The Finned Enclosure differs the Simple Enclosure in such a way that it has five circular fins mounted on the inner face and they are distributed uniformly along the length. These fins are embedded into the phase change material and touch the cell. It is to be noted that the computational geometries are rotationally symmetric. Therefore, we have an advantage to compute the solutions on two-dimensional

domains to reduce the computational cost. The computational geometries for the two designs are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Computational domain with (a) Simple Enclosure and (b) Fined Enclosure

The material properties of the cell, PCM and the enclosure are given in the following tables.

Table 1. The material properties of the lithium-ion cell.

Property	Value	Unit
Density	2092	Kg/m ³
Thermal conductivity	18.2	W/(m-k)
Specific heat	678	J/(Kg-K)

Table 2. The material properties of the PCM RT-27.

Property	Value	Unit
Density	760	Kg/m ³
Thermal conductivity	0.2	W/(m-k)
Specific heat	2000	J/(Kg-K)
Latent heat	189	KJ/Kg
Viscosity	0.02	Kg/(m-s)
Solidus temperature	297.5	K
Liquidus temperature	299.5	K

Table 3. The material properties of aluminum.

Property	Value	Unit
Density	2719	Kg/m ³
Thermal conductivity	202.4	W/(m-k)
Specific heat	871	J/(Kg-K)

3. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In this section, we give some flow and thermal assumptions and the governing equations of the problem.

3.1 Flow and Thermal Assumptions

- (a) The problem under consideration is a 2D, laminar, incompressible and transient problem.
- (b) The density of the PCM is assumed to be constant and radiations are ignored.

(c) The material properties of the materials are constant in order to observe the pure melting process to compare the two geometric designs.

(d) The enthalpy-porosity method is used for the melting of PCM because this method does not require the liquid-solid interface during the melting process [23-26]. This method considers the computational domain to be porous. The porosity of all the cells is determined by liquid fraction γ , which

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } T < T_s \\ \frac{T - T_s}{T_l - T_s}, & \text{if } T_s < T < T_l \\ 1, & \text{if } T > T_l \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

3.2 Mathematical Model

The mathematical model that governs the flow is

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u}) = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho \vec{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u} \vec{u}) = \mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} - \nabla p - \rho \vec{g} + \vec{S}_u, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho H)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u} H) = \nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla T), \quad (4)$$

where t , \vec{u} , p and \vec{g} are the time, velocity vector, pressure and gravitational acceleration respectively. H is the enthalpy, which is the sum of the latent enthalpy ΔH and sensible enthalpy h_s , i.e.,

$$H = \Delta H + h_s, \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta H = \gamma L_h, \quad (6)$$

$$h_s = h_{ref} + \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_p dt, \quad (7)$$

where γ is the liquid fraction, L_h is the latent heat of fusion, h_{ref} is the reference enthalpy at T_{ref} . For fins, only heat conduction is considered governed by the equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_{fin} c_{p,fin} T) = \nabla \cdot (\lambda_{fin} \nabla T). \quad (8)$$

The boundary conditions at the external boundaries and interfaces of the lithium-ion cell, PCM and metallic enclosure and fins are as follows.

Table 4. Thermal and flow boundary conditions.

Sr. No.	Location	Thermal condition	Flow condition
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takes 0 for the solid phase and 1 for the liquid phase.

A source term \vec{S}_u , where $\vec{S}_u = A_{mush} \frac{(1-\gamma)^2}{\gamma^3 + \epsilon} \vec{u}$ is included in the momentum equations to identify the solid zone, the mushy zone, and the liquid zone, where A_{mush} is the mushy zone constant, ϵ is small number whose value is taken to be 1×10^{-3} to avoid 0 in the numerator in \vec{S}_u . The γ is calculated as

1.	Top boundaries	$\frac{\partial T_{cell_top}}{\partial n} = 2500 \text{ W / m}^2,$ $\frac{\partial T_{PCM_top}}{\partial n} = \frac{\partial T_{enclosure_top}}{\partial n} = 0$	$u = v = w = 0$
2.	Bottom boundaries	$\frac{\partial T_{cell_bottom}}{\partial n} = \frac{\partial T_{PCM_bottom}}{\partial n}$ $= \frac{\partial T_{enclosure_bottom}}{\partial n} = 0$	$u = v = w = 0$
3.	Finned enclosure outer wall	$\frac{\partial T}{\partial n} = 0$	$u = v = w = 0$
4.	PCM-fin interface	$T_{PCM} = T_{fin},$ $k_{fin} \frac{\partial T_{fin}}{\partial n} = k_{PCM} \frac{\partial T_{PCM}}{\partial n}$	$u = v = w = 0$
5.	PCM-cell interface	$T_{PCM} = T_{cell},$ $k_{PCM} \frac{\partial T_{PCM}}{\partial n} = k_{cell} \frac{\partial T_{cell}}{\partial n}$	$u = v = w = 0$
6.	Solid PCM-liquid PCM interface	$T_{S,PCM} = T_{L,PCM}$ $k_{S,PCM} \frac{\partial T_{S,PCM}}{\partial n} = k_{L,PCM} \frac{\partial T_{L,PCM}}{\partial n}$	$u = v = w = 0$

which means that a heat flux of 2500 W/m^2 enters into the lithium-ion cell from the top.

$$\frac{\partial T_{cell_top}}{\partial n} = 2500 \text{ W / m}^2 \quad (9)$$

The remaining external boundaries in the computational domain are thermally insulated while the internal boundaries define interfaces between the cell, PCM and the metallic enclosure and fins. The centerline boundary of the cell is rotationally symmetric.

The boundary conditions are as under.

The initial conditions are as below.

$$t = 0, T_0 = 294 \text{ K}, u = v = w = 0. \quad (10)$$

4. SOLUTION PROCEDURE

We solve the flow problem numerically using Finite Volume Method which is built-in in ANSYS Fluent 16.2. All the tasks of simulations, i.e., geometry creation, meshing, choice of models, solution and

postprocessing have been performed using ANSYS. For solution, SIMPLE scheme is used for the pressure-velocity coupling. For spatial discretization, the Green-Gauss Cell-Based method is used for the gradient calculations, second order interpolation is used for the pressure for enhanced accuracy in the pressure-velocity coupling, and second order upwind scheme is used for the momentum and energy equations. The threshold for the residuals is set to below 10^{-3} for continuity, momentum equations while it is 10^{-6} for the energy equation. The calculations are performed unless the PCM melts completely.

5. MESH INDEPENDENCE STUDY

For mesh independence study, two mesh densities namely Mesh 1 and Mesh 2 are compared for cell

temperature and liquid mass fraction. Both mesh configurations are the structured mesh with a skewness very close to zero. Mesh 1 has 3380 elements while Mesh 2 has 7030 elements. Despite this significant increase in element count, the results for both the cell temperature and the liquid mass fraction demonstrated negligible variations, as may be

seen in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The close alignment of the corresponding temperature curves and the liquid fraction curves from both models indicates that the numerical solution has achieved a level of grid independence, suggesting that the coarser mesh provides a sufficiently accurate resolution for capturing the essential physics of the problem.

Figure 2. Cell temperature curves for Mesh 1 and Mesh 2 vs time in seconds.

Figure 3. Liquid fraction curves for Mesh 1 and Mesh 2 vs time in seconds.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we give detailed discussion of the influence of the enclosure design on cell temperature and melting of the PCM.

6.1 Transient Thermal and Phase Change Response

In Figure 4, we can see that the initial temperature of the lithium-ion cell is 294 K. Its temperature rises quickly from 294 K to 298 K for both the Simple Enclosure and the Finned Enclosure in a time duration of about 270 seconds. After 298 K, the rise of the cell temperature slows down for both the designs, but it is clear that the temperature is lower in case of the Finned Enclosure. This is because the heat

is distributed by the Finned Enclosure more uniformly into the PCM and the PCM starts melting at more locations as compared to the Simple Enclosure design which is evident from the liquid fraction curves in Figure 5 and also from subsequent contours graphs. The temperature curves rise almost linearly during the melting of the PCM. After about 80% of PCM melt, the slope of the temperature curves again rises for both the cases, as combinedly observed Figures 4 and 5. From Figure 5, it is clear that the PCM melts completely before 2000 seconds, which indicates that the PCM has completed its role and there is need of active cooling strategy to keep the battery in operational mode.

Figure 4. Cell temperature curves for Simple Enclosure and Finned Enclosure

In Figure 5, the liquid fraction remains zero until achieving the melting temperature of the PCM. After 270 seconds, the PCM starts melting and liquid fraction curves rise linearly while the slope of the

curve for Finned Enclosure is higher due to uniform distribution of the heat into the PCM. This is why the melting of PCM is completed earlier for Finned Enclosure as compared to the Simple Enclosure.

Figure 5. Liquid fraction curves for Simple Enclosure and Finned Enclosure

6.2 Spatial Thermal and PCM Liquid Fraction (Contour Analysis)

In this subsection, we discuss the local response of the lithium-ion cell and the PCM with the help of contours graphs. After each 300 seconds, the contours graphs are captured for temperature and liquid fraction for both the Simple Enclosure and the Finned Enclosure designs and are side-by-side placed in the text in Figure 6 to Figure 11.

In Figure 6(a) and (b), we see that the heat is entering into the lithium-ion cell from the top boundary because it has the highest temperature in the domain. At the same time, we observe also that the temperature is distributed more uniformly into the computational dome in case of Finned Enclosure design, Figure 6(b). The impact of this uniform temperature distribution is also seen in Figure 6(c) and (d) where we see that the liquid fraction is covering more space in the Finned enclosure design. As the time increases, the heat spreads into the

domain towards both the axial and the radial directions. The pattern of the contours is similar during the whole process.

In Figure 10, after 1500 seconds, the contours pattern is similar as the previous. The temperature distribution is non-uniform in the Simple Enclosure design as compared to the Finned Enclosure. The liquid fraction contours in Figure 10(c) and (d) show that the PCM is fully melt in the upper part of the domain in Finned Enclosure case, while in the Simple Enclosure case, there is uneven melting showing clearly the importance and impact of the enclosure design. Battery thermal management is significantly enhanced by integrating the PCM with an optimal enclosure design.

In Figure 11, after 1800 seconds, we again see a similar pattern as previously observed. Also, we see that the PCM is fully melt in case of Finned Enclosure, while it is still on the way in case of Simple Enclosure.

Figure 6. Temperature contours (a) Simple Enclosure, (b) Finned Enclosure, and Liquid fraction contours (c) Simple Enclosure, (d) Finned Enclosure after 300 seconds.

Figure 7. Temperature contours (a) Simple Enclosure, (b) Finned Enclosure, and Liquid fraction contours (c) Simple Enclosure, (d) Finned Enclosure after 600 seconds.

Figure 8. Temperature contours (a) Simple Enclosure, (b) Finned Enclosure, and Liquid fraction contours (c) Simple Enclosure, (d) Finned Enclosure after 900 seconds.

Figure 9. Temperature contours (a) Simple Enclosure, (b) Finned Enclosure, and Liquid fraction contours (c) Simple Enclosure, (d) Finned Enclosure after 1200 seconds.

Figure 10. Temperature contours (a) Simple Enclosure, (b) Finned Enclosure, and Liquid fraction contours (c) Simple Enclosure, (d) Finned Enclosure after 1500 seconds.

Figure 11. Temperature contours (a) Simple Enclosure, (b) Finned Enclosure, and Liquid fraction contours (c) Simple Enclosure, (d) Finned Enclosure after 1800 seconds.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The current study focusses on investigating the impact of cell enclosure design on melting of phase change material for the purpose of thermal

management of lithium-ion cell. For this, two design are considered namely, Simple Enclosure and Finned Enclosure and the PCM considered is RT-27. Findings of the present work are:

1. The temperature and the liquid fraction curves show that the temperature can be regulated significantly using PCM during the operational conditions.
2. Finned Enclosure distributes the heat into the PCM more uniformly as compared to the Simple Enclosure.
3. The gap in temperature curves for both the designs reaches up to 3.5 units which shows the importance of enclosure design.
4. The metallic inserts are required in radial as well as axial direction for a uniform spread of heat in the PCM.
5. The complete melting of the PCM occurs earlier in case of the Finned Enclosure.

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